

Generations and Gender Study UK Technical report

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Generations and Gender Survey

Background

The University of Southampton received funding from the Economic Social Research Council (ESRC) to conduct the first wave of the Generations and Gender Survey (GGS) in the UK. The GGS is part of a series of panel surveys to understand families, life course trajectories and gender relations. This is encompassed within the Generations and Gender Programme (GGP) and aims to understand demographic and social developments among several countries in Europe as well as other countries, for example, Hong Kong and Kazakhstan. The UK survey launched in 2022 and finished in 2023. Further information can be found on the GGP website www.ggp-i.org

The UK version of the GGS aims to understand the family dynamics of those between 18-59. There is a specific focus on fertility, relationship with children, partner formation or dissolution alongside more general concepts such as a participant's wellbeing. The intent is that the survey can be used to understand family planning and behaviour within the UK.

Summary of the study

The Generations and Gender Survey was launched in the United Kingdom as a nationally representative online study of individuals aged between 18 to 59 years old. The survey followed a mobile-first design principle, catering toward smaller screen sizes, however the survey was fully 'device-agnostic' and so could be completed on mobile devices as well as on a desktop PC/laptop. One individual within the selected household was invited to take part in the study, and all households received one invitation letter alongside two reminders.

The letters contained information on how to participate via the online survey, the access code, and details about the project's aims and legal rights for processing data. Fieldwork was separated into two stages - stage 1 and stage 2. Stage 1 of fieldwork launched on September 28th 2022 and stage 2 fieldwork commenced on January 12th 2023, and ended February 19th. This decision to split the fieldwork into two parts was to support an experimental incentive offering in stage one which would influence stage two.

A total of 7,876 individuals took part in the survey, with 7,204 having fully completed the survey and an additional 672 partial completions through to the end of the life history module. Stage one had a total of 3,755 completes and Stage two received 4,121 completed interviews.

Sampling

The UK Generations and Gender Survey required a sample which was representative of the population of those 18-59 in the United Kingdom. The survey aimed to achieve 7,000 productive interviews with UK adults aged 18-59 living in private accommodation. The survey used a push-to-web approach to recruit participants. Under this method, a stratified random-probability sample of addresses was drawn from the Postcode Address File (PAF).

In 2022 an unclustered sample of 84,650 addresses was drawn from the Postcode Address File (PAF). Prior to selection, all PAF addresses within Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland were sorted by: IMD quintiles, Local Authority Area and postcode. Within England, addresses were additionally sorted by region (GOR) prior to IMD quintiles, Local Authority Area, and postcode. A systematic (1 in N) random sample of addresses was then drawn. The list of sampled addresses was randomly split into two stages and one reserve sample. The reserve sample was not used, as issuing the main sample was sufficient to meet the target of 7,000 completed interviews.

Where selected addresses contained more than one eligible individual (i.e. aged 18-59) a quasi-random selection of one individual per household was requested, taking the birthdays of all eligible household members into account. The household member carrying out the eligibility screening was instructed to pass the survey to the individual who most recently had a birthday among all eligible household members, so that that person could complete the questionnaire: If the person with the most recent birthday happened to be the household member carrying out the eligibility screening, then they would be prompted to complete the survey themselves. If the person with the most recent birthday was a different member of the household, then they would ideally have been passed the survey to complete the survey. However, if that other household member refused to take part or if it was not possible to pass the survey to them at that time, then two scenarios were possible: If the person completing the eligibility screening was aged 18-59 then they were prompted to complete the survey instead of the person with the most recent birthday. Alternatively, if the person completing the eligibility screening had declared that they were not aged 18-59, then they were routed out of the survey and displayed a message stating that the selected individual (i.e. most recent birthday) could complete the survey at a later time if it was not possible to hand them the survey currently.

Selected households were sent an invitation letter and two reminder letters inviting them to take part in the GGS. Based on an incentive experiment within stage one (households were randomly assigned differing values of vouchers of £10, £15 and £20), stage two used a targeted differential incentive based on IMD decile was applied where addresses within the 10% most deprived IMD decile were offered a higher incentive of £20 while the rest of the remaining issued sample was offered £15.

To achieve this increased expenditure within budget for stage two 1,750 addresses from the initial stage two sample were removed randomly before being contacted.

Usability testing

As a part of the redesign process NatCen undertook for the GGS questionnaire, several cognitive interviews and usability tests were conducted on the initial GGS Life Histories module. Usability is a design perspective that focuses on the users (e.g., survey respondents) of the system (e.g., computer), typically applied in human-computer interaction since the rise of computer-assisted interviewing (CAPI). Whereas cognitive interviewing methods are derived from cognitive psychology and allow researchers to examine the mental processes people go through when completing surveys. Cognitive interviewing techniques focus on four processes: whether participants comprehend the information provided, how they recall information necessary to assist with the task, the judgments (or shortcuts) they make as to what information to provide and how they respond to the request (Tourangeau et al. 2000). User-testing interviews are used to establish whether a product meets end user requirements and respondents are able to interact with the developed instrument in the intended manner.

Broadly the purpose of testing was to explore:

- Understanding of key terms within the questions;
- Whether respondents were able to select a suitable response option;
- Sensitivity of questions and difficulty answering them.

The testing aimed to examine the impact of life history summary tables which existed to prompt participant with a summary of their responses from prior modules. Another strand of investigation was improving data accuracy and quality, as well as testing the effectiveness of summary tables using Blaise 5 software. A total of 12 interviews were conducted with participants, all of whom were aged between 18-59 and many had complex relationship and/or family histories. The 'cogability' interviews (the combined method of cognitive interviewing to test how users understand question wording, with usability testing to test screen layout on devices of different sizes and ease of navigation) were employed to understand both the mental judgement participants undertake and also the user interactions of the instrument mobile and compute devices (Wilson and Dickinson 2021)

The findings resulted from the cogability interviews were presented by the NatCen research team detailing recommendations for modification of questions. This process informed the questionnaire alterations and deviations from the standard GGS questionnaire, another focus of the interviews was the inclusion of summary screens.

For more information on the cogability interview process and outcome, see the GGS user report at [GGP-Technical-Report-on-life-history-summary-tables.pdf \(soton.ac.uk\)](https://soton.ac.uk/ggp-technical-report-on-life-history-summary-tables.pdf).

Questionnaire design and development

The design of the UK questionnaire was based on the international Generations and Gender Survey (www.ggp-i.org). The UK questionnaire was adapted to include UK-specific questions or improve question wording. Enhancements were also made to improve the questionnaire design and reduce break-off.

A detailed breakdown of the UK survey changes can be found in a supplementary Excel document hosted on the GGP website <https://www.ggp-i.org/data/methodology/>

Information about variable names and variable codes (as found in the UK dataset) is provided below to help users identify UK-specific deviations from the pre-existing GGS data structure when merging and analysing alongside other countries.

Variable names

Data variables that relate to questions only asked in the UK are named in a particular way to ensure that they are easily identifiable. As such, all of the UK-only question variables include the **suffix** _4301, _4302, _4303, etc. (where “02”, “03”, etc. implies the variable is a further iteration of the concept underlying the “01” variable). The remainder of the variable name (i.e. the portion before the suffix) takes as its reference the variable that it is conceptually closest to from the pre-existing bank of GGS questions, as identified by the GGP team.

For example, the UK question “dem15b” is called “**dem15_4301**” in the data because the question it is conceptually closest to (from the pre-existing bank of GGS questions) is “dem15”.

Sometimes an additional letter is included before the suffix to indicate that the original question concept has been split. For example, the “a” and “b” in dem09**a**_4301 and dem09**b**_4301 indicate that the original question dem09 “How many rooms do you have?” has been split into two separate questions: “How many bedrooms are there?” (dem09**a**_4301) and “How many living or dining rooms are there?” (dem09**b**_4301).

Sometimes an additional suffix (_1, _2, _3, etc.) is included to indicate that this is the n^{th} answer that a respondents gave to a **multicode** question. For example, fer07a_1_4301 represents the first answer given to the multicode question, fer07a_2_4301 represents the second answer given, fer07a_3_4301 the third answer given, and so on.

Data users should therefore be mindful of the fact that the **data variable name** (as found in the dataset) does not necessarily resemble the **question name** exactly (as shown in the UK questionnaire), and should also note that the supplementary Excel document of UK survey changes mirrors the dataset.

The table below provides a look-up for the UK-specific variable names as found in the dataset against the question names as found in the questionnaire:

Dataset name	Questionnaire name	Module
dem09a_4301	DEM09	Demographics
dem09b_4301	DEM09a	Demographics
dem15_4301	DEM15b	Demographics
lhi25_4301	LHI24X_	Life Histories
fer14_4301	FER14a	Fertility
fer07_4301	FER07Bin	Fertility
fer07a_1_4301	FER07a	Fertility
fer07a_2_4301	FER07a	Fertility
fer07a_3_4301	FER07a	Fertility
fer07a_4_4301	FER07a	Fertility
fer07a_5_4301	FER07a	Fertility
fer07a_6_4301	FER07a	Fertility
fer07a_7_4301	FER07a	Fertility
fer07a_8_4301	FER07a	Fertility
fer07a_9_4301	FER07a	Fertility
fer07b_1_4301	FER07b	Fertility
fer07b_2_4301	FER07b	Fertility
fer07b_3_4301	FER07b	Fertility
fer07b_4_4301	FER07b	Fertility
fer07_4302	FER09Bin	Fertility
fer07a_1_4302	FER09a	Fertility
fer07a_2_4302	FER09a	Fertility
fer07a_3_4302	FER09a	Fertility
fer07a_4_4302	FER09a	Fertility
fer07a_5_4302	FER09a	Fertility
fer07a_6_4302	FER09a	Fertility
fer07a_7_4302	FER09a	Fertility
fer07a_8_4302	FER09a	Fertility
fer07a_9_4302	FER09a	Fertility
fer07b_1_4302	FER09b	Fertility
fer07b_2_4302	FER09b	Fertility
fer07b_3_4302	FER09b	Fertility
hhd13f_4301	HHD13f	Households
gen52a_1_4301	GEN52b	Generations
gen52a_2_4301	GEN52b	Generations
gen52a_3_4301	GEN52b	Generations
gen52a_4_4301	GEN52b	Generations
gen52a_5_4301	GEN52b	Generations

Dataset name	Questionnaire name	Module
gen52a_6_4301	GEN52b	Generations
gen52a_7_4301	GEN52b	Generations
gen52a_8_4301	GEN52b	Generations
gen52a_9_4301	GEN52b	Generations
gen52a_10_4301	GEN52b	Generations
gen52a_4301	GEN52c	Generations
gen52b_1_4301	GEN53a	Generations
gen52b_2_4301	GEN53a	Generations
gen52b_3_4301	GEN53a	Generations
gen52b_4_4301	GEN53a	Generations
gen52b_5_4301	GEN53a	Generations
gen52b_6_4301	GEN53a	Generations
gen52b_7_4301	GEN53a	Generations
gen52b_8_4301	GEN53a	Generations
gen52b_4301	GEN53b	Generations
gen57m_4301	GEN57a (month)	Generations
gen57y_4301	GEN57a (year)	Generations
wrk09_4301	WRK09a	Work
wrk16a_4301	WRK16c	Work
wrk36_4301	WRK36a	Work
wrk42_4301	WRK42b	Work
wrk50_4301	WRK25P	Work
att03j_4301	ATT03l	Attitudes
att06d_4301	ATT06c	Attitudes
att12b_4301	WRY01a	Attitudes
att12c_4301	WRY01b	Attitudes
att12e_4301	WRY01c	Attitudes
att12f_4301	WRY01d	Attitudes
att12g_4301	WRY01e	Attitudes
att12i_4301	WRY01f	Attitudes
att12j_4301	WRY01g	Attitudes
att16_4301	BET01	Attitudes
att16_4302	BET02	Attitudes
att12_4305	RSK01	Attitudes
att17_4301	BREXIT	Attitudes
att18_4301	ETH11	Attitudes

Variable codes

For pre-existing GGS questions asked in their original form, the code structure remains unchanged.

For questions only asked in the UK, codes are numbered in the expected manner, i.e. 1 for the first answer option, 2 for the second option, etc.

For pre-existing GGS questions that have been adjusted to improve clarity for the UK survey:

Answer options that are the same or consistent with the pre-existing question are represented by the same code value as before.

In a small number of cases, the wording of the answer options has changed slightly without significantly changing the interpretation of the option. In such cases, where the meaning of the UK-specific answer option was deemed to be directly comparable with the pre-existing answer option, the code has been kept the same as the pre-existing GGS question.

Answer options that are new for the UK survey or that have been altered for the UK survey (and are no longer directly comparable with any equivalent answer options from the pre-existing question) are numbered in the following manner to identify that the code represents a UK-specific deviation: **43##**

The **##** element represents the order number within the range of UK-specific codes, e.g. 4305 is the fifth UK-specific code listed for the given variable.

For example, question **dem07** “What is the highest level of education you have completed?” has been altered so that the answer options reflect the UK education system, as shown below. Some answer options were added/altered, whilst some answer options were kept the same. The below example also demonstrates that answer options that were removed from the UK questionnaire are omitted from the UK data variable code list.

Pre-existing data variable:

- 0, Early childhood education
- 1, Primary education
- 2, Lower secondary education
- 3, Upper secondary education
- 4, Post-secondary non tertiary education
- 5, Short cycle tertiary education
- 6, Bachelor or equivalent
- 7, Master or equivalent
- 8, Doctoral or equivalent

UK data variable:

- 4301, Primary or less
- 4302, Some secondary
- 4303, Secondary up to age 16
- 4304, Further post-16 education or training
- 6, Bachelor's or equivalent
- 7, Master's or equivalent
- 8, Doctoral or equivalent

Data users should also note that in a few variables the missing values are different in the UK data (reflecting the changes to non-response answer options in the UK questionnaire), with some missing values categories removed or added. These deviations are also recorded in the detailed breakdown in a separate document hosted on the GGP webpage <https://www.ggp-i.org/data/methodology/>.

Summary of UK-specific changes to the questionnaire

Outlined below is a summary of the main changes to the pre-existing questionnaire that were implemented for the UK survey.

General:

Some questions were removed from the UK survey, and are not included in the data structure. Other questions were altered from the international GGS standard in order to improve data quality. Using cognitive interviewing, we tested the best format for the following questions, paying particular attention to answers recorded on a smartphone.

Questions regarding the frequency of events were altered in some cases to include an option for per “day” (in addition to per “week”, “month” and “year”) and in most cases to include an option for “less than once a year”.

Questions asking for a date (month and year) were changed so that responses were no longer recorded in a formatted text box (MM/YYYY). Instead the respondent was asked to choose from a list of months and enter the year in a text box, with the option to refuse or answer “don’t know” to either the month, the year, or both.

Questions asking for a time response (hours and minutes) were changed so that that responses were no longer typed into a single formatted text box (HH:MM). Instead the hours and minutes were asked for separately (on the same screen). This deviation, like some others was based on user testing.

Validation checks (soft checks or hard checks) were also added to various frequency, month/year, and hours/minutes questions to improve data quality.

Questions where respondents were asked to provide a response based on a scale of 0 to 10 were asked differently in the UK Survey. An example of the scale questions are the satisfaction questions: 0 = “not at all satisfied”; 10 = “completely satisfied”. Respondents were no longer asked to provide the chosen scale number in a text box, and were instead presented with a visual 0 to 10 scale on screen and asked to tick against the scale number of choice. They were also presented with text descriptions for each of the scale end-points, and in most cases the scale mid-point too, (e.g. 0 = “not at all satisfied”; 5 = “average”; 10 = “completely satisfied”) to help improve reliability of response and avoid bias towards the extremities of the scale.

A small number of response options were altered to make them more relevant for UK respondents (e.g. options for the question “How did you meet [your partner]?” include reference to a “pub”).

Likewise, a few response options were altered to reflect changes in how certain concepts are referenced (e.g., “ill or disabled for a long time or permanently” was changed to “long-term sick or disabled”).

A few questions were also altered so that the answer options were worded using an alternative grammatical form or common vocabulary, with the aim of improving comprehension. Likewise, some question examples were presented to the respondent after the question stem to help with comprehension.

A small number of questions were altered by collapsing previously separate answer options into a single answer category where it was deemed that the individual items did not have sufficient analytical value on their own.

Questions about the respondent’s occupation and the occupations of partners and parents included an additional option “occupation is not listed”. Selecting this option provided the respondent with an opportunity to write a job title in a free-text box. Data users should note that this verbatim occupation data was not re-coded and is only presented in the data as “occupation is not listed”.

Questions posed in Euro currency were instead posed in Pounds Sterling.

Statements of confidentiality were added to various questions to reassure respondents that they would not be personally identifiable from the data. These were implemented at the questions deemed most sensitive and the questions about other people (e.g., ex-partners, children, other household members).

Gender:

The question “What is your gender?” (**dem01**) was amended to “What is your sex?”, and this was followed up by the question “Is the gender you identify with the same as your sex registered at birth?”. The follow-up question included an upfront option to refuse to answer and a free-text box to enter a gender identity in words if preferred, rather than providing a yes/no answer only.

These changes were made for ethical reasons and to reflect changing attitudes toward sex and gender, thereby minimizing the sensitivity and enhancing the inclusivity of this element of the survey. The approach taken for the UK survey broadly follows the guidance and principles laid out by the ONS in its development of sex and gender identity questions for the 2021 Census:

<https://www.ons.gov.uk/census/censustransformationprogramme/questiondevelopment/sexandgenderidentityquestiondevelopmentforcensus2021>

However, data for the follow-up gender identity question (including the free-text verbatim responses) is not available in the public-access dataset for reasons of confidentiality.

Data users should also note that for reasons of data harmonisation with the international GGS standard questionnaire variable dem01 is labelled in the dataset as “Gender”, even though the question asks about sex (as a distinct concept from gender).

Questions that were previously routed off the original question “What is your gender?” (**dem01**) remained unchanged (i.e., routing was still filtered off the same question, even though the question wording/meaning had changed to “What is your sex?”).

The subsequent question about whether the respondent’s partner is male or female (**dem23**) was altered in the question wording so that the respondent was explicitly asked about their partner’s sex (male/female), whereas the pre-existing question made no reference to either gender or sex.

Unlike the partner male/female question, the equivalent questions about each of the respondent’s children (**lhi28**) and each of the respondent’s other household members (**hhd05**) were not altered in the question wording, and so made no reference to either gender or sex. However, these children / other household members questions did include a third option of “other” in addition to “male” and “female”.

Current activity status:

Questions regarding the current activity status of the respondent (**dem06**), their partner (**dem26**), their children (**lhi35**), and other members of their household (**hhd07**) were presented slightly differently in the UK survey:

- Code 1 was presented as “In education, training, or apprenticeship” rather than “In education or training” to account for the prevalence of apprenticeships in the UK
- Code 4 was presented as “Unpaid work for family business” rather than “Helping family member in a family farm or business” to make the unpaid aspect of the work more explicit
- Code 6 “Retired” was not present for question **lhi35**, as it was deemed that children of the respondents would be too young to be retired
- Code 7 “In military or civic service” was not presented to UK respondents as there is no compulsory national service in the UK
- Code 11 was presented as “Long-term sick or disabled” rather than “Ill or disabled for a long time or permanently” to mirror the wording that would typically be used in the UK to describe this status

Education:

Questions relating to the respondent’s education (**dem07**) and the education of their partner (**dem25**) / father (**gen49**) / mother (**gen51**) have been altered to so that the answer options reflect the UK education system.

Number of rooms:

The original GGS question **dem09** “How many rooms do you have?” was replaced by two questions:

How many bedrooms are there? (**dem09a_4301**)

How many living or dining rooms are there? (**dem09b_4301**)

The change was made to improve validity and reliability, by providing specific reference points as to what rooms should be included in the respondents’ answers.

Social media use (new question):

A new question on social media use was added (**dem15_4301**), as it is widely used in the UK today: “On a typical day, about how many hours do you spend on social media? With social media we mean e.g., Instagram, Twitter, Facebook, YouTube or Tinder”

Partner questions:

The question about whether the respondent had a partner (**dem21**) – which was a filter question for all subsequent partner-related questions – was altered slightly to clarify that it must be an “intimate” partner, but also to clarify that this would include partners who are not co-resident:

“We are interested in both opposite and same sex partners who you have been in a relationship with. Do you have an intimate partner now even if you don’t live with them?”

Because we did not expect many non-coresidential intimate partners to have been previously married, we removed questions that asked whether the respondent was previously married to that partner (**dem33**), and dates of marriage and divorce (**dem33am**, **dem33ay**, **dem34m**, **dem43y**).

Civil partnerships:

The question “Are you and your partner legally married?” (**dem28a**) was altered to include “or civil partnerships”, because the prevalence of civil partnerships in the UK is very low and did not require a separate question.

This meant that respondents in a civil partnership were routed to the same questions as those in marriages.

Consequently, separate questions about being a in “registered partnership” were removed (**dem29a**, **dem29bm**, **dem29by**).

Child questions:

References to stepchildren in the international standard GGS questionnaire were replaced in most instances with references to a partner’s or ex-partner’s children (i.e. children from before the respondent’s relationship with the partner or ex-partner), most notably at the summary screen which asks the respondent to confirm the number of children reported (**lhi20**). Whilst some clarification was given to respondents in the pre-existing questionnaire as to what a stepchild was defined as, the UK questionnaire removed references to stepchildren where appropriate to avoid confusion and to broaden the scope of children to be included in the respondent’s answers. It was deemed that “stepchildren” could be interpreted to have a narrower meaning (e.g. a child that the respondent has knowingly taken on as stepchild), whereas “partner’s or ex-partner’s children” would encompass more widely any child of a partner or ex-partner (from before the respondent’s relationship with them), regardless of the respondent’s own relationship with that child or their status in relation to that child.

Questions around the death of a child (biological, adopted, or children belonging to a partner or ex-partner) were changed to minimize sensitivity and survey burden. In the UK questionnaire, the respondent was asked if any of the children reported had passed away (**lhi25_4301**). Only if a death was reported at this filter question would they get asked to confirm for each individual child if they were still alive (**lhi25**); those respondents that did not report a death therefore did not need to confirm this for each child. By contrast, the international standard GGS questionnaire asked whether each child was still alive (for all respondents with children), rather than establishing from the outset if any child had passed away.

To reduce further respondent burden, the routing of the child questions was revised to avoid asking unnecessary questions. For example, the respondent was not asked to confirm if a child was their biological child, an adopted

child, or the child of a partner/ex-partner (**lhi26**), if the answer to that question was logically attainable from answers given at preceding questions.

Additionally, some of the later child questions were asked in a different order in the UK survey compared to the international GGS standard questionnaire. This was to facilitate an alternative routing structure with the aim of simultaneously reducing respondent burden (where possible) and improving the logical flow of the questions.

GGS standard questionnaire order:

LHI33u, LHI35, LHI36, LHI37, LHI38, LHI39a, LHI39au, LHI39b, LHI39bu, LHI40

UK survey order:

LHI33u, LHI38, LHI39a, LHI39au, LHI39b, LHI39bu, LHI35, LHI36, LHI37, LHI40

One of the changes to routing was based on the addition of a new category at the filter question “Is [child name] currently living in the same household with you?” (**lhi31**), namely: “I don’t know anything about this child/person”. This was to account for children with whom the respondent does not have a relationship with (e.g. ex-partner’s children), and meant that the respondent did not have to get routed to subsequent questions about that child.

The filter question “Is [child name] currently living in the same household with you?” (**lhi31**) was also used to make other routing changes to the UK questionnaire, with the aim of routing to subsequent questions only when it would be logically relevant to the respondent/child.

Likewise, further routing changes intended to avoid asking unnecessary question were made on the basis of whether the respondent met with or had contact with the child.

Fertility questions:

An additional question was added to capture whether a respondent currently expecting a child intended to have more (biological) children in future (**fer14_4301**).

The question “How many more children - including biological and adoptive children - do you intend to have overall?” (**fer16a**) was changed to remove reference to the type of children, namely: “How many [more] children do you intend to have?”

Questions about the impact, considerations and social perceptions of having a child (or another child) were removed from the UK survey (**fer25a to fer27c**).

The questions about fertility diagnoses were split so that there were separate questions for/about females (**fer07a_#_4301** for respondent; **fer07a_#_4302** for partner) and separate question for/about males (**fer07b_#_4301** for respondent; **fer07b_#_4302**). This was done so that the list of answer options could be tailored to whether the question was about a male or a female (e.g. “poor sperm count/quality” only featuring in the male version of the question).

For the question “Have you or your partner ever done any of these things to help you get pregnant?” (**fer11**) the option “none of the above” was replaced with “no, haven’t done anything to help get pregnant”. This was done because “none of the above” was deemed to be open to a wider interpretation (i.e. could be interpreted to mean that the respondent was doing something to help get pregnant which was not present in the available answer options).

Likewise, for the question “Are you or your partner using or doing any of these things to prevent pregnancy at this time?” (**fer12**) the option “none of the above” was replaced with “no, not doing anything to prevent pregnancy” for similar reasons. The option “other method” was also added to the response list. Routing to this question was also changed to exclude people who had already responded that they or their partner had been sterilised or had an operation that makes it impossible to have children. The routing condition of being under 50 years old was also removed.

Data users should note that for reasons of data harmonisation with the international GGS standard questionnaire certain codes are listed differently in the dataset compared to how they appeared in the UK questionnaire, and may have a slightly different interpretation when considered in combination with the question stem and the other codes present at the question:

- (**fer11**) code 8 was presented to respondents as response option “No, haven’t done anything to help get pregnant” but is listed in the dataset as “None of the above”
- (**fer12**) code 14 was presented to respondents as response option “No, not doing anything to prevent pregnancy” but is listed in the dataset as “None of the above”

Household questions:

A new question was added at the end of the battery of questions related to who usually does certain household tasks. The new question (**hhd13f_4301**) asked about who usually drops off and picks up children at childcare/school. This question was originally asked in the Swedish version of the GGS.

The wording of the question “Do you get regular help with childcare from a day care centre, a nursery or pre-school, an after school care centre, a self-organised childcare group, a babysitter, or from some other institutional or paid arrangement?” (**hhd22**) was revised to simplify the question and to focus the question on paid professional childcare only, namely: “Do you regularly pay a childcare provider, childminder, or nanny?”

The wording of the question “Over the last 12 months, have you given help with childcare to other people?” (**hhd25**) was changed to focus the question on regular help, and to exclude work done by childcare workers, namely: “Over the last 12 months, have you given regular help with childcare to other people? If you are a childcare worker, please consider only the help you have given outside of your job.” Additionally, a pre-existing GGS follow up question was added back into the UK survey: “How frequently have you given help with childcare to other people?” (**hhd27** for frequency and **hhd27u** for unit).

Generations questions:

The questions about the respondent’s parents (from **gen03** onwards) were reworded to clarify that the respondent should answer about their ‘biological’ parents.

Pre-existing GGS questions were added back into to the UK survey regarding both the respondent’s biological mother and father (questions for mother asked separately from question about father):

- For the past six months at least, to what extent has your mother/father been limited because of a health problem in activities people usually do? (**gen17** for mother, **gen31** for father)
- How long does it take to get from your home to where your mother/father lives at present? (**gen21** for mother, **gen35** for father)

Some questions were removed:

- In which year did your biological father have his first child? (**gen41b**)

-
- Where did you live for most of your childhood, that is until you were 15? (**gen42**)
 - Plus subsequent questions where lived, i.e., country/region (**gen43** to **gen44b**)

The question “Have you ever lived separately from your parents for at least three months?” (**gen52**) was changed to clarify what was meant by living separately, namely: “Have you ever moved out of the parental home for at least three months? Please include going to college or university and living away from your parents’ home during term time, as moving out of your parents’ home. Do not include going to boarding schools.”

New questions were added to capture information on:

- why respondents had moved out of the parental home (**gen52a_#_4301** and **gen52a_4301**)
- why respondents were still living with one or both of their parents or still in the parental home (**gen52b_#_4301** and **gen52b_4301**)

Questions about grandchildren were altered, in the first instance by being routed on the basis of whether the respondent’s oldest child (as declared in the Life Histories module) was reported as being older than 15 years old (rather than explicitly asking the respondent if they had any grandchildren). Furthermore, respondents were now asked to provide the birth month and year of their youngest grandchild (**gen57m_4301** and **gen57m_4301**), as well as their oldest grandchild (**gen57m** and **gen57y**). Note that previously the questionnaire only asked about the oldest grandchild.

The questions about the respondent receiving regular help with personal care were removed from the UK survey (**gen58** to **gen63**).

Wellbeing questions:

The question “Who usually makes decisions about health care for yourself?” (only routed if the respondent had a partner) was removed (**wel02a**).

Questions about weight and height were altered to allow the respondent to respond in imperial measurements if desired as an alternative to responding in metric measurements, as imperial measurements are more commonly used in the UK. However, the final data has been converted fully to metric measurements, i.e. centimetres and kilograms (**wel06** and **wel07**).

Data users should note that for reasons of data harmonisation with the international GGS standard questionnaire certain codes are listed differently in the dataset compared to how they appeared in the UK questionnaire, and may have a slightly different interpretation when considered in combination with the question stem and the other codes present at the question:

- (**wel02**) code 20 was presented to respondents as response option “No” but is listed in the dataset as “None of the above”
- (**wel10**) code 22 was presented to respondents as response option “I don’t discuss important personal matters with anyone” but is listed in the dataset as “Nobody”

Work questions:

The following questions were removed:

- satisfaction with current employment status (**wrk01**)
- whether working full-time or part-time (**wrk06**)
- whether intending to give up paid work in the next three years (**wrk16b**)

Additionally, a number of partner-related work questions were removed (**wrk38** to **wrk41**, and **wrk47** to **wrk49**).

The following questions were added:

- time of day that best represents the respondent's normal working hours (**wrk09_4301**)
- "If you were to lose your job, how likely do you think it is that you would find an equivalent job within twelve months?" (**wrk16a_4301**)

Equivalent questions were also added regarding the respondent's partner (**wrk36_4301** and **wrk42_4301**).

Additionally, a question was added to capture whether partners currently on maternity or paternity leave intend to work after their leave has ended (**wrk50_4301**).

Income questions:

Some of the questions were removed from within the battery of questions concerning items that the household can afford. The questions that were removed were deemed to be about items that were the least expensive amongst range of items asked about in the battery of questions (**inc04d** to **inc04f**, and **inc04i** to **inc04k**).

The question about income received from different sources in the last 12 months (**inc08**) included new options for "earnings from other household member's paid work" (by which was meant someone other than the respondent or their partner) and "a Universal Credit payment". Options for "a widow or survivor or war benefit", "a social assistance payment" and "a study benefits or a scholarship" were removed. Additionally, the follow-up questions were removed asking about:

- (**inc09**) how often income was received from each income source
- (**inc11**) the average monetary amount received from each income source

Data users should note that the code "None of the above" was not present in the UK survey at question **inc08**. Instead respondents were allowed to leave the question empty (as has been in the case in previous GGS surveys).

Attitudes questions:

The following questions based on the Swedish GGS were added:

- (**att03f**) A woman can have a child as a single parent even if she doesn't want to have a stable relationship with a man (5-point scale: strongly agree – strongly disagree)
- (**att03j_4301**) A pre-school child is likely to suffer if his/her father spends too much time at work (5-point scale: strongly agree – strongly disagree)
- (**att06d_4301**) Children should invite their parents to live with them when parents can no longer look after themselves due to financial difficulties (5-point scale: strongly agree – strongly disagree)
- (**att12b_4301** to **att12j_4301**) Thinking about the future, how much does the following worry you?
 - Climate change
 - Overpopulation / population pressure
 - Economic crisis / rising prices
 - Increased number of refugees
 - High unemployment
 - Military conflict
 - Global epidemics

-
- (att16_4301) When your children will be of your age, do you think they will be better off than what you now are?
 - (att16_4302) Compared to your parents when they were at your age, do you consider yourself better off than they were?
 - (att12_4305) Would you describe yourself as someone who tries to avoid risk (risk averse) or someone who likes to take chances (a risk taker)?

The following questions were only asked in the UK GGS:

- (att17_4301) In the Brexit referendum, you were asked, 'Should the United Kingdom remain a member of the European Union or leave the European Union?' Did you vote to 'remain a member of the EU' or to 'leave the EU'?
- (att18_4301) What is your ethnic group?

Questions regarding “whether parents should help their adult children” (att05b) and “who should take care of elderly parents” (att06a and att06b) were reworded to instead focus on “how parents and their adult children can help each other”. This aligns with the wording for att06d_4301 also (as mentioned above).

The following questions were removed:

- (att03g) To what extent do you agree or disagree [with the following statement]? A child needs a home with both a father and a mother to grow up happily
- (att07b) For whom is a university education more important, men or women? (5-point scale: men definitely – women definitely)

Fieldwork

Mainstage

The GGS was split into two fieldwork stages in order to facilitate experiments on incentives and QR codes. Each stage was allocated approximately half of the total sample (43,200 for stage one and 41,450 for stage two, due to subsampling). Stage one launched on the 28th September 2022 with Stage two launching on 12th December 2022. Fieldwork closed on the 19th February 2023.

Table 1 GGS Fieldwork dates

Stage 1	28/09/2022 - 10/01/2022
Stage 2	12/01/2023 - 19/02/2023

Stage one offered conditional incentives of either £10, £15, or £20. Stage 2 offered a conditional incentive of £15 to the majority of the sample, except for those with postcodes ranked at the lowest Index of Multiple Deprivation (IMD) decile, who were offered a £20 conditional incentive. Stage two fieldwork also included a QR experiment, in which half of the issued sample were sent an invitation and reminder letters with generic QR codes included for ease of survey access.

Communication Strategy

The communications strategy used for both stages was identical. These were designed to ensure that each successive contact built on the last, with an attempt to vary the motivational statements to increase the likelihood of converting non-responders.

There were three attempts to contact respondents to take part in the survey, as outlined in table 2. All mailings were sent second class and addressed to the resident.

The content of the communications used the principles of social exchange, a theory which posits that individuals respond to requests on the basis of perceived rewards they trust will be received by responding to the request, and belief that the rewards (either personal or social) will outweigh the perceived costs of participation. Benefits of participation which were emphasised include: explaining how the results will be used; financial incentives for participation; and the benefits having additive effects. Steps that were taken to reduce the perceived costs included emphasising the simplicity of the task; maximising the ease of participation; and avoiding the need for uncomfortable answers.

All households received an invitation letter in the post, followed by a reminder letter approximately 2 weeks later. The second reminder excluded households that had already completed the survey or had opted out of receiving any further correspondence with NatCen prior to the reminder 2 sample creation. Reminder 2 was mailed out approximately one week after reminder 1.

Each mailing was scheduled to be sent out on different days of the week, in order to account for variability in household's availability across the week. Letters were also sent out through Second Class postage, which typically arrives within 1 to 3 working days after posting (including Saturdays).

Table 2 Mailing Dates

Communication	Mailing Date
Stage 1: Invitation	27/09/2022
Stage 1: Reminder 1	07/10/2022
Stage 1: Reminder 2	19/10/2022
Stage 2: Invitation	11/01/2023
Stage 2: Reminder 1	21/01/2023
Stage 2: Reminder 2	09/02/2023

Letter Design

The invitation and reminder 2 mailings were sent out in white C5 envelopes, while reminder 1 was sent out in a manilla C5 envelope. This was to encourage potential households who dismissed the initial (invitation) white envelope to open the subsequent mailing (reminder 1).

All initial letter mailings comprised of a double-sided personalized letter (page 1 being the invitation or reminder, and page 2 being a 'frequently asked questions' (FAQ) segment) and a resources leaflet. The FAQ page explains the aim of the GGS, who funds it, whether participation is voluntary, who NatCen are, how their contact details were collected, what will be done with their information provided during the survey, safeguarding regulations, and NatCen contact details. See the [appendix](#) for more information on the FAQ page.

The resources leaflet is a 2-page document providing respondents with contact details for useful services, had they been affected by the topics raised during the GGS. It provides telephone numbers and/or website links to services such as Relate (relationship advice), Mind (mental health advice), Samaritans (general issues/concerns), and Citizens Advice (general issues/concerns). See the [appendix](#) for more information on the resources leaflet.

All 3 letters provided key information on the aim of the GGS and clear instructions on how to take part. Instructions were presented in a numbered list, highlighted by a turquoise box to draw attention. Within the instruction list, respondents were provided with the survey link, their unique access code, and the value of their conditional incentive. We also experimented with whether a QR code would facilitate ease of use and/or affect response rates. Thus, half of the stage 2 letters included a QR code and the other half only included a link to the survey. See the [appendix](#) for more information on the invitation and reminder letters.

Both the URL and access codes excluded the use of ambiguous characters to ease survey access. The key information needed to access the survey was also in bold text to highlight its importance. This follows ONS guidance on push-to-web social surveys – for more information see <https://analysisfunction.civilservice.gov.uk/policy-store/respondent-engagement-for-push-to-web-social-surveys/>

The reminder letters used the same overall structure as the invitation letters, but with differing introductory paragraphs. The invitation letter introduced the GGS as an online survey about families, individuals, and work, stating that their household has been chosen to take part. It explained who the study was aimed at, how long it would take, and the deadline for completion.

The reminder 1 letter reminded households that they would have recently received an invitation from NatCen regarding an online survey about life in the UK. It referenced the cost-of-living crisis and its impact on job security and family structures. The reminder 2 letter informed households that the study was drawing to a close and reminded them of the conditional incentive offered. It referenced the importance of completing the survey (it helps policymakers understand how people's lives are changing), and how taking part will allow respondents to voice their concerns about the future. An additional sentence was added to the 'How long will it take?' section in reminder 2, providing well known examples of where the conditional incentive can be spent.

Incentive experimentation

The incentive experiment was applied to the stage 1 sample using a responsive design. This determined which incentive values would be best utilised at stage 2, with the aim to maximise response rates while remaining cost efficient. At stage 1, either a £10, £15, or £20 conditional incentive treatment was assigned at random to 3 representative groups (14,400 issued sample per group). Stage 2 incentive offerings were then determined based off of stage 1 experimentation results.

Of the total stage 2 issued sample, approximately 90% were offered a £15 incentive, while 10% were offered a £20 incentive. The £20 incentive offer was only allocated to addresses in the lowest IMD decile for each individual country (England, Wales, Scotland, and Northern Ireland). The IMD decile is the official measure of relative deprivation for small areas across the country. Wales, Scotland, and Northern Ireland have their own respective deprivation measures (WIMD, SIMD, and MDM). For more information on the English indices of deprivation, see <https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/english-indices-of-deprivation>. This was done to increase response rates in areas that were otherwise less likely to engage in the GGS.

In order to achieve the increased incentive offering within budget, the total issued sample for stage 2 was reduced to 41,450 – just less than half of the total sample size for the GGS.

QR Experimentation

Stage 2 also included a QR experiment in which exactly half (20,725) of the issued sample were provided with an additional QR code on their invitation and reminder letters. This was implemented to test QR code usage against the standard login URL usually provided, and its impact on response rates.

Handling Queries

All letter communications sent to households included contact details for the bespoke project website, project phone number, and project email in order for respondents to easily get in touch with queries regarding the GGS. The project email and phone line were managed by NatCen's freephone team. Freephone members were able to provide respondents with clarification on the GGS, mainly through directing respondents towards the project website page or the survey link and aiding in the distribution of incentives. The research team also aided in resolving more complex queries received via email or phone.

Participation in web surveys is often hindered by the need to manually type the survey URL provided via letter into an internet browser. Respondents tend to either mistype the URL or enter the URL into the search bar

instead of the address bar, which makes accessing the survey far more difficult. Therefore, to maximise participation in the GGS a bespoke website URL was purchased. The URL was short and excluded the use of slashes to ensure simplicity and avoid respondents mistyping the link. The website provided respondents with easily accessible information on the project, including an FAQ, privacy notice, useful resources, direct survey link, and contact details.

Survey outcome and response rates

In total, 84,650 addresses were sampled, during stage one the project experimented with incentive offerings (£10, £15, £20 vouchers) which influenced the incentive procedures for stage 2. Stage two, alongside incorporating a tailored incentive design, also experimented with Quick Response (QR) codes for half of the sample. Stage one issued 43,200 addresses with stage two having 41,450 household being issued. The lower sample was issued in stage two as the incentive procedure was altered to offering £15 to 90% of the sample and £20 offered to those in the top 10% most deprived areas.

There were a total of 7,876 interviews across the two stages. A total of 7,204 were fully completed interviews, with an additional 672 partially productive cases who disengaged with the survey after fully completing the life history modules. Combining partially and fully productive completes stage one had a total of 3,755 completes and Stage two received 4,121 completed interviews.

Table 3 Survey Outcomes

	Stage one	Stage two	Total
Issued	43,200	41,450	84,650
Assumed eligible households	26,111	25,533	51,644
Fully productive	3,464	3,740	7,204
Partially productive	291	381	672

This represents a response rate of 8.7% in Stage one and 9.9% in Stage two, however after adjusting for deadwood and assumed eligibility (no one aged 18-59) the adjusted response rate is 14.1% in Stage 1 and 16.1% in stage 2.

The assumed eligibility of 31.5% is the proportion of households which contain no 18-59 year olds (Source: Quarterly Labour Force Survey Household Dataset, July - September, 2021, accessed: 1 February 2022). Whereas the PAF deadwood figure (10%) is an estimate based on recent PAF surveys. The combined figure is 38.4% because the 10% deadwood applies to all PAF addresses, while the 31.5% is applied to the 'eligible' PAF addresses (i.e., the 90%).

Weighting

Selection of addresses

In 2022 an unclustered sample of 84,650 addresses was drawn from the Postcode Address File (PAF). Prior to selection, all PAF addresses within Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland were sorted by: IMD quintiles, Local Authority Area and postcode. Within England, addresses were additionally sorted by region (GOR) prior to IMD quintiles Local Authority Area and postcode. A systematic (1 in N) random sample of addresses was then drawn. The list of sampled addresses was randomly split into two stages and one reserve sample. The reserve sample was not used, as issuing the main sample was sufficient to meet the target of 7,000 completed interviews.

Based on an incentive experiment within stage one, a targeted differential incentive based on IMD decile across the sample was applied where addresses within the most deprived IMD decile were offered a higher incentive. To achieve this within budget 1,750 addresses from the initial stage two sample were removed randomly.

Selection of individuals

Where selected addresses contained more than one person aged 18-59 a quasi-random selection of one individual per household was requested. Persons were instructed to hand the survey to the individual with the next birthday among all eligible household members.

Weighting

Weights were generated for the GGS responding sample in order to control for known sources of bias. The sampling design accorded every UK address an equal probability of being selected, while at each address one household was invited to take part. Address selection weights were therefore not required. However, as only one person per household was allowed to respond, selection bias within households could occur. Hence, the weighting scheme consisted of within-household selection weights, non-response modelling, and a calibration to population estimates. These three steps are described in detail below.

Non-response modelling

Certain subgroups in the population are less likely than others to respond to surveys, which is referred to as differential non-response. These groups can end up being under-represented in the responding sample, introducing bias to the survey estimates. To adjust for this, household response was modelled using logistic regression, with the dependent variable indicating whether or not someone at each selected address responded to the survey. Stepwise logistic regression was used to fit the model. Variables that described the character of the area in which a selected address was located, including aggregated census data and deprivation indices, were tested for association with response.

The final non-response model included the following variables:

- Region (GOR) including Scotland, Wales, and NI,
- Population density quintiles,
- Output area classification (OAC) social group,
- Percentage of families with children in area (quintiles),
- Percentage of social grade AB in area (quintiles),
- Percentage of area residents with a degree (quintiles),

-
- Percentage of BAME area residents (quintiles),
 - Percentage of area residents aged 55 or above (quintiles),
 - Urban/rural classification.

The full model is shown in appendix table 1.

A non-response weights was generated from the inverse of the model's estimated probability of response for each responding address. This NR weight was checked for efficiency and residual bias. An untrimmed version used as trimming at the 99th percentile produced no noticeable improvement in either efficiency or bias.

Within-household selection weights

People in households with more than one eligible dweller had a lower chance of selection than single occupants. To account for this, we calculated a within-household selection weight that equals the number of eligible household members. I.e., in a household with 3 eligible people, the respondent received a selection weight of 3. To avoid extreme weights, we capped the selection weights at 3. A second option with selection weights capped at 4 were explored too, but then discarded due to efficiency and bias reasons.

Calibration

The final stage of weighting was to adjust the composite non-response weight (the product of within-household selection weight and non-response weight) so that the weighted composition of the sample was in line with the best available population estimates of the characteristics of adults aged 18-59 in the UK. Population estimates were taken from Office for National Statistics for age, sex and region, and the latest ONS Labour Force Survey (LFS) for education, ethnicity, economic activity and housing tenure. The final calibration matrix contained the following variables:

- Age categories by sex,
- Region (GOR),
- Highest level of education by age categories,
- Ethnicity,
- Housing tenure,
- Economic activity.

After calibration the weights were checked for outliers. Trimming the top weights did not improve efficiency, so the untrimmed version was chosen as the final weight. This final weight was scaled to the sample size, giving it a mean of 1.

The weighting variable **weight_4301** is the product of the aforementioned calibration, selection, and non-response modelling. Variables **psu_4301** and **strata_4301** correspond to the Primary Sampling Units and stratum or subgroups used when sampling.

Weighting efficiency and effective sample size

The effect of the weights on the precision of the survey estimates is indicated by the effective sample size (neff). The effective sample size measures the size of an (unweighted) simple random sample that would achieve the same precision (that is, the range of the standard error associated with each estimate) as the design that has been implemented. The efficiency of a sample is given by the ratio of the effective sample size to the actual sample size. The effective sample size (neff) of GGS after weighting is 5,609 with an efficiency of 71%.

Data outputs

The University of Southampton and Netherlands Interdisciplinary Demographic Institute (NIDI) who coordinate GGS and the wider Generation and Gender Programme (GGP) received a full cumulative Stata dataset including derived, geo-demographic and weighting variables at the end of the survey. Anonymised data will be made available to download through the UK Data Service (UKDS) as a Special Licence version as a SPSS file. The Special Licence has been implemented due to the dataset containing detailed variables and potentially disclosive material, users of these data have to fill out an application form to make the case as to how they will be using the data.

Data protocol

This chapter outlines the key conventions and structure of the datafile.

Missing value conventions

The missing values in the data files are defined in the following way:

- **Missing (-1)**. A value of -1 is applied in instances where the respondent has been routed away from the question, for instance, if a question is filtered based on a previous response and that question is not relevant to the respondent. Additionally, as multicode questions are represented by a separate variable for each answer given by the respondent (e.g. a variable suffixed “_1” represents the respondent’s first answer selected, another variable suffixed “_2” represents the respondent’s second answer selected, and so on), then the code -1 is applied once the respondent has stopped giving further answers. For example, if the respondent gave two answers to a multicode question, then the variables suffixed _1 and _2 would be populated with the codes corresponding to their answers, but variables suffixed _3, _4, etc. will be coded -1.
- **Don’t know (-8)**. Where a respondent has answered that they do not know the answer to a question. Don’t know options were available for the majority of all questions.
- **Refusal (-9)**. Where the respondent has explicitly answered that they do not want to give a response to the question. This option was available for the majority of all questions
- **Incomplete Survey (-7)**. Where the respondents has disengaged or broken off from the survey they will have a missing value of -7 to any question after they disengaged.
- **Not applicable (-6)**. This value is present where there is no prior routing and a question assumes an experience, behaviour or element of their life so the respondent could inform us the question was not relevant.

There are also a handful of question-specific missing values:

- **Occupation is not listed (-11)**. Where a respondent has answered their own, or another person’s occupation is not provided in the database.
- **Not working or homemaker (-10)**. A value of -10 is where a respondent has selected not working or homemaker at occupation question.
- **Never (-5)**. Present as an option for most of the questions beginning “How often...?”.
- **Mainly work from home (-3)**. Present as an option where the respondent has been asked distance from their employment (wrk08).
- **Not at all (-4)**. Present as an option for two questions concerning how many hours mothers/fathers should work (att11b and att11d).
- **Don’t own a property (-2)**. Present for a question about property sale value (inc01).

References

Tourangeau, R., Rips, L. J., & Rasinski, K. (2000). The psychology of survey response.

Wilson, L., & Dickinson, E. (2021). *Respondent Centred Surveys: Stop, Listen and Then Design*

Appendix

Figure 1 - Invitation letter

Figure 2 Reminder 1 letter

Figure 3 - Reminder 2 letter

<add1>
<add2>
<add3>
<add4>
<add5>
<Postcode>

Your reference: P17181 <HHSerial>/<CKL>

Dear Resident,

We wrote to you recently to invite you to take part in an online survey about individuals' lives in the UK. **The study is drawing to a close and this is your last chance to get a voucher.** This study is crucial for understanding how people's lives are changing. It will inform policymakers about families and households, work and fairness, and your concerns about the future. If you have already completed the survey though, please accept our thanks and ignore this letter.

Taking part is voluntary, and you will be asked a range of questions about yourself and, if applicable, your partners and children, including a small number of sensitive questions, which you may choose not to answer if you wish.

How to take part

- 1 Go to the survey on your mobile or computer: mysurvey.natcen.ac.uk/GGS
- 2 Enter your unique access code: <Acc1> - <Acc2> - <Acc3>
- 3 Complete the survey and receive a £<VouchType> voucher as a thank you

<QRInstr1>
<QRInstr2>

<QRcode>

How long will it take?

The survey will take about 50 minutes of your time. You will then receive a £<VouchType> **Love2Shop voucher** to spend at retailers like Argos, TK Maxx, Waterstones, PizzaExpress and many more.

Who should take part?

We would like one adult aged between 18 and 59 in your household to take part. If there is more than one adult, then the person who most recently had a birthday should take part.

When should I complete it by?

We have extended the deadline to take part. The survey now ends **Tuesday 1st November**, but please take the survey as soon as possible so you don't miss out!

Thank you for your support,

Brienna Perelli-Harris
Professor of Demography
University of Southampton

Shane Howe
Research Director
National Centre for Social Research

✉ GGS@natcen.ac.uk ☎ 0800 652 4568 🖱 GGS.natcen.ac.uk

P17181_GGS_RemLet2 - V1

Frequently asked questions

What is this project?

The Generations and Gender Survey (GGS) aims to collect information from 7,000 people from the United Kingdom. It is part of an international collaboration with 20 countries that have already taken part. The GGS provides data on families, partnerships and life courses and is part of the Generations and Gender Programme. To find out more visit: www.ggp-i.org

Who is funding this project?

The University of Southampton in partnership with the Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC) are funding the Generations and Gender Survey. The ESRC is the largest research council in the UK: www.ukri.org/councils/esrc

Do I have to take part?

No, it is entirely up to you to decide whether or not to take part. Your participation is voluntary and you may withdraw within 14 days for any reason. However, if you withdraw from the study after that time, it may not be possible to remove the data once your personal information is no longer linked to the data.

Who are the National Centre for Social Research (NatCen)?

NatCen is Britain's largest independent social research agency. For over 50 years, they have worked with charities, government and academic institutions to find out what people really think about big issues. They are independent of all government departments and political parties.

How did you get my contact details?

We have selected a random sample of addresses from a list of all addresses in the UK, kept by the Post Office. This is to make sure that the survey represents the whole country. The findings will not be able to identify you or your family.

What will you do with the information I give?

Your information is treated in the strictest confidence under current data protection legislation. The results are used for statistical purposes only. If you provide consent, NatCen will store contact data securely for up to five years in order to contact you in the future about how your life has changed.

How do you safeguard my privacy?

All your information will be held until no longer required, in accordance with current data protection legislation. Under this legislation, University of Southampton are the 'Data Controllers' and NatCen are the 'Data Processors' on behalf of University of Southampton. We will both hold your information on the basis of 'Legitimate Interest'. If you agree, then your contact information will be held for up to 5 years to allow us to recontact you.

If you want to learn more about how we safeguard your privacy, your data and your rights you can read our data protection policy at GGS.natcen.ac.uk/Privacy or contact the NatCen Data Protection Officer by email: dpo@natcen.ac.uk. If you have a complaint, please contact the University of Southampton Research Integrity and Governance Manager (023 8059 5058, rgoinfo@soton.ac.uk).

How can I contact you?

To get in touch you can email us at GGS@natcen.ac.uk or call us on 0800 652 4568.

NatCen Social Research, Kings House, 101-135 Kings Road, Brentwood, Essex CM14 4LX Tel. 0800 526 397. Company limited by guarantee. Reg No. 4392418. A Charity registered in England and Wales (1091768) and in Scotland (SC038454). University of Southampton Ethics number: 75541.

Figure 5 - Resources leaflet letter (page 1)

Generations and Gender Survey (GGS) 2022

Resources leaflet

Thank you very much for your help with this study. If you have any questions or comments, please feel free to contact NatCen Social Research on freephone 0800 652 4568.

NatCen Social Research is an independent, not for profit social research organisation. We are aware that taking part in surveys may raise issues about which you might like further advice and support. This information sheet provides you with some telephone numbers and services which you may find useful.

Figure 6 - Resources leaflet letter (page 2)

Contact us for further information

Please contact us if anything about the survey concerns you.

You can withdraw from the study within 14 days for any reason. However, if you withdraw from the study after that time, it may not be possible to remove the data once your personal information is no longer linked to the data.

You can contact NatCen Social Research by writing to 35 Northampton Square, London, EC1V 0AX; calling on freephone **0800 652 4568** or emailing **GGS@natcen.ac.uk**

The GGS research team is from NatCen Social Research (NatCen), University of Southampton (SOTON) and the Generations and Gender Programme

Relate

For support and advice on a range of relationship issues, visit **relate.org.uk/**

Mind

For information and advice on mental health, visit **mind.org.uk/**
Call: **0300 123 3393** 9am-6pm Mon-Fri
Email: **info@mind.org.uk**

Samaritans

For counselling and advice on any issue of concern, visit **samaritans.org/**
Call: **116 123**
Email: **jo@samaritans.org**

Citizens Advice

For support on a variety of issues. Local offices are available throughout UK.

Phone (England): **0800 144 8848**

Phone (Wales): **0800 702 2020**

Phone (Scotland): **0800 028 1456**

Phone (N.Ireland): **see website**

Website (Eng/Wal): **citizensadvice.org.uk/**

Website (Scotland): **cas.org.uk/**

Website (N.Ireland): **citizensadvice.org.uk/about-us/northern-ireland/**

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Appendix Table 1: non-response model.

	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% C.I. for EXP(B)	
							Lower	Upper
Region			67.79	11	0			
North East								
North West	-0.12	0.07	3.01	1	0.08	0.89	0.78	1.02
Yorkshire and the Humber	0.12	0.07	2.77	1	0.1	1.12	0.98	1.29
East Midlands	-0.04	0.07	0.36	1	0.55	0.96	0.83	1.11
West Midlands	-0.1	0.07	1.85	1	0.17	0.91	0.78	1.04
East of England	-0.12	0.07	2.77	1	0.1	0.89	0.77	1.02
London	-0.29	0.08	12.55	1	0	0.75	0.64	0.88
South East		0.07	0.4	1	0.53	0.96	0.84	1.1
South West	0.03	0.07	0.15	1	0.7	1.03	0.89	1.18
Scotland	-0.09	0.11	0.58	1	0.45	0.92	0.73	1.15
Wales	-0.28	0.08	11.66	1	0	0.76	0.65	0.89
Northern Ireland	-0.21	0.08	6.72	1	0.01	0.81	0.69	0.95
Population density of postcode sector (in quintiles)			8.05	4	0.09			
1 (lowest)								
2	0.07	0.04	2.81	1	0.09	1.07	0.99	1.17
3	0	0.05	0.01	1	0.91	1	0.91	1.09
4	0.09	0.05	3.28	1	0.07	1.09	0.99	1.19
5 (highest)	0.05	0.06	0.65	1	0.42	1.05	0.94	1.17
Percentage social grade in quintiles			7.6	4	0.11			
1 (lowest)								
2	0.03	0.05	0.41	1	0.52	1.03	0.93	1.15
3	0.09	0.07	1.64	1	0.2	1.09	0.96	1.24
4	0.11	0.08	1.97	1	0.16	1.12	0.96	1.3
5 (highest)	0.01	0.09	0.01	1	0.94	1.01	0.84	1.21
Percentage with degree in quintiles			21.69	4	0			
1 (lowest)								
2	0.12	0.05	4.75	1	0.03	1.12	1.01	1.25
3	0.09	0.07	1.79	1	0.18	1.09	0.96	1.24
4	0.23	0.08	8.54	1	0	1.25	1.08	1.46
5 (highest)	0.35	0.09	14.36	1	0	1.41	1.18	1.69

Percentage of 55+ in quintiles			37.37	4	0			
1 (lowest)								
2	-0.13	0.04	10.68	1	0	0.88	0.81	0.95
3	-0.19	0.05	17.41	1	0	0.82	0.75	0.9
4	-0.24	0.05	20.82	1	0	0.79	0.71	0.87
5 (highest)	-0.36	0.06	36.44	1	0	0.7	0.62	0.78
Percentage of People with children in quintiles			21.69	4	0			
1 (lowest)								
2	-0.24	0.06	17.01	1	0	0.78	0.7	0.88
3	-0.08	0.05	2.55	1	0.11	0.92	0.83	1.02
4	-0.08	0.05	3.11	1	0.08	0.92	0.84	1.01
5 (highest)	-0.02	0.04	0.14	1	0.7	0.98	0.91	1.07
Urban/Rural indicator	0.1	0.04	6	1	0.01	1.11	1.02	1.21
OAC super-group			18.18	7	0.01			
Rural Residents								
Cosmopolitans	0.04	0.08	0.23	1	0.63	1.04	0.89	1.22
Ethnicity central	-0.13	0.09	2.06	1	0.15	0.88	0.73	1.05
Multicultural metropolitans	-0.11	0.08	2.01	1	0.16	0.9	0.78	1.04
Urbanites	-0.02	0.05	0.21	1	0.65	0.98	0.88	1.09
Suburbanites	-0.14	0.05	7.21	1	0.01	0.87	0.78	0.96
Constrained city dwellers	-0.1	0.07	2.2	1	0.14	0.91	0.8	1.03
Hard pressed living	-0.09	0.06	2.76	1	0.1	0.91	0.81	1.02
Percentage ethnic minorities in quintiles			11.22	4	0.02			
1 (lowest)								
2	0.06	0.04	2.38	1	0.12	1.07	0.98	1.16
3	-0.02	0.05	0.14	1	0.71	0.98	0.9	1.08
4	0	0.05	0	1	0.98	1	0.9	1.11
5 (highest)	-0.13	0.07	3.14	1	0.08	0.88	0.76	1.01
Constant	-2.17	0.09	556.99	1	0	0.11	0	0

